

ANTIMUTAGENIC ACTIVITY OF MAILLARD REACTION PRODUCTS AGAINST MUTAGENIC HEATED TAUCO

ATTIVITÀ ANTIMUTAGENICA DEI PRODOTTI DELLA REAZIONE DI MAILLARD
NEI CONFRONTI DELLA MUTAGENICITÀ DEL TAUCO RISCALDATO

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ABSTRACT

The mutagenicity of ethanolic extracts of sweet and salty tauco heated under various conditions was assayed with both SD 510, a streptomycin dependent strain of *Salmonella typhimurium* TA 98 and the original strain of histidine and biotin dependent TA 98. Mutagenicity of both taucos increased with the increase in heating temperature and time (15 to 45 min). Antimutagenic activity of Maillard reaction products prepared from lysine-glucose was higher than that of glycine-glucose against the mutagenicity of both taucos. The highest antimutagenicity was observed in reaction products prepared by heating at 120°C for 30 min at pH 11.

RIASSUNTO

La mutagenicità degli estratti etanolici del Tauco dolce e salato, riscaldati in modi diversi, è stata saggiata con SD 510, un ceppo streptomicina-dipendente di *Salmonella typhimurium* TA 98 e con il ceppo originale TA 98, istidina e biotina dipendente. La mutagenicità dei due Tauco aumenta all'aumentare della temperatura e del tempo di riscaldamento (da 15 a 45 minuti). L'attività antimutagenica dei prodotti della reazione di Maillard, saggiata sulla mutagenicità del Tauco, risulta più alta sui prodotti ottenuti da lisina-glucosio rispetto a glicina-glucosio. L'antimutagenicità più elevata è presente nei prodotti di reazione preparati per riscaldamento a 120°C per 30 minuti a pH 11.

- Key words: antimutagenic activity, Maillard reaction products, tauco -

INTRODUCTION

Tauco is a traditional fermented food in Indonesia, usually made from yellow soybean. After cooking, it is served as a condiment in various dishes due to its particular meat-like flavor. Tauco is relatively high in protein which is mostly composed of glutamic acid (USMAN and HOSONO, 1996). No report has been published regarding the formation of mutagens in tauco, although a number of researchers have reported that mutagens can be produced during cooking of protein-rich foods. SUGIMURA and WAKABAYASHI (1990), YAMAMOTO et al. (1978), KASAI et al. (1980) and FELTON et al. (1984) isolated some mutagenic and/or carcinogenic compounds from products of heat decomposition of various amino acids, cooked meat and fish, and food-grade beef extract. YOSHIDA et al. (1978) reported the formation of 2-amino-9H-pyrido[2,3-b]indole (A α C) and 2-amino-3-methyl-9H-pyrido[2,3-b]indole (MeA α C) from soybean globulin during the pyrolysis process. Other investigators have also reported the effect of cooking conditions on the formation of mutagens in foods. PARIZA (1982) studied the effect of time and temperature on the mutagen formation in ground beef during frying, and concluded that mutagen formation in fried ground beef is temperature dependent. BJELDANES et al. (1983) also studied the effect of cooking time and temperature on the mutagen formation in meat crust and found that mutagenic activity in the crust increases with cooking time, but time is less important than temperature.

Later, HOSONO et al. (1987b) studied and compared the mutagen formation on pork cured with or without spices, and then heated at different times and temperatures. They observed that heat-induced enhancement of mutagen formation was attributed mainly to the presence of spices in the curing formula. On the other hand, the amino-car-

bonyl reaction of amino acids with sugar, usually called Maillard browning reaction, is a typical reaction that takes place during processing, cooking, and storage of foods.

YEN et al. (1992) reported the antimutagenic effects of Maillard reaction products (MRPs) prepared by heating three sugars (fructose, glucose and xylose) and four amino acids (arginine, glycine, lysine and tryptophan) at 100°C for 10 h, and found that MRPs prepared from sugars-tryptophan and xylose-amino acids strongly inhibited the mutagenicity of 2-amino-3-methyl-imidazo [4,5-f]quinoline (IQ), 3-amino-1,4-dimethyl-5H-pyrido[4,3-b]indole (Trp-P-1) and 2-amino-6-methyldipyrido[1,2- α :3'2'-d]imidazole (Glu-P1) toward *Salmonella typhimurium* TA 98 in the presence of S-9 mix.

Other investigators have also studied the antimutagenic effect of MRPs prepared from different solutions containing a sugar and an amino acid, such as glycine-glucose (KATO et al., 1985; LEE et al., 1994), cysteine and phenylalanine with glucose or fructose (KONG et al., 1989) by heating at different temperatures and pHs, and assaying the antimutagenic activity using *Salmonella typhimurium* TA 98 in the presence of S-9 mix. Recently, we also reported that MRPs prepared from lysine-glucose and glycine-glucose by heating at 120°C for 30 min at pH 11.0 have strong desmutagenicity against Trp-P-1 toward the SD 510 strain, assayed in the absence of S-9 mix (HOSONO et al., 1997). In this study, we illustrate that extracts of heated tauco exhibited a dose-related mutagenicity against the SD 510 strain and that the Maillard reaction products of lysine-glucose and glycine-glucose prepared by heating at various temperatures lower than 120°C for 30 min at pH 7.0, or at 120°C for 30 min under various pH conditions exhibited antimutagenic activity against sweet and salty tauco toward the SD 510 strain.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of sweet and salty tauco

Sweet and salty taucos, purchased at a market in Bogor, Indonesia, were blended to a fine paste and heated to a temperature from 60 to 120°C for 15 to 120 min. Each heat treated sample (50 g) was extracted with 50 mL of 99% ethanol and centrifuged at 2000 x g for 10 min. The supernatant was taken and then sterilized by filtering the extract through a membrane filter (0.45 µm) (Fuji Film Co., Tokyo, Japan).

Preparation of Maillard reaction products

Maillard reaction products were prepared according to HOSONO et al. (1997). In brief, the pH values of an aqueous solution of 1 M lysine and glycine with equimolar glucose were adjusted to 3.0, 5.0, 7.0, 9.0 and 11.0. Each solution in a reaction tube was capped and heated at 60, 80, 100 or 120°C for 30 min.

Preparation of the S-9 mix

A metabolic activation of S-9 prepared from male Sprague-Dawley rat liver induced with phenobarbital and 5,6-benzoflavone, and cofactor-I were purchased from Oriental Yeast Co., Ltd, Osaka, Japan. Nine mL of sterile distilled water and 1 mL of S-9 were put into one vial of cofactor-I and mixed well. The S-9 mix was prepared and used immediately depending on the treatments.

Tester strains of Salmonella used for the mutagenicity assay

Strains SD 510 and TA 98 were used. SD 510 was grown in Oxoid Nutrient Broth No. 2 (Unipath, Basingstoke, UK) containing 20 µg/mL of streptomycin

(SM 20). TA 98 was maintained as per the protocol (MARON and AMES, 1983).

Bacterial mutagenicity

Mutagenicity studies were carried out according to MARON and AMES (1983). The SD 510 strain was grown in SM 20 broth overnight to an OD of 1.3 at 660 nm (5.0×10^8 cfu/mL) in a shaking water bath at 37°C. The culture was suitably diluted with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and 0.1 mL of culture was used in the assay. Both plate incorporation and disc assay tests were conducted.

Disc assay was performed as described by THYAGARAJA and HOSONO (1993). Ethanol extracts of salty or sweet tauco of various concentrations with or without the S-9 mix were applied on a paper disc placed in a previously lawned OX plate. All the plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 h and observed for revertants as well as zones of inhibition developed due to toxicity. The number of streptomycin-independent revertant colonies formed were scored. Optimum concentration of mutagen to induce maximum revertants with minimum toxicity as well as the requirement of the S-9 mix was determined for establishing the dose response.

Dose response was established by the plate incorporation method, a modification (YAHAGI et al., 1975) of the method of AMES et al. (1975), in which the preincubation step precedes the addition of the top agar. The mutagen and tester strain were incubated at 37°C for 30 min. Each tauco extract was also tested in multiple doses ranging from the observed effect level to toxicity. In a mutagenicity assay, 100 µL of the 1000 times diluted SD 510 culture, 30 µL tauco extract sample and 300 µL of S-9 mix, and in an antimutagenicity assay, 30 µL tauco extract and 200 µL of Maillard reaction products of lysine-glucose or glycine-glucose were added and mixed in a test tube, and preincubated at 37°C

for 30 min. One hundred μL of the SD 510 culture and 300 μL of the S-9 mix were added to the preincubation mixture for the antimutagenicity assay, followed by 2 mL molten top agar (nutrient broth with 0.5% agar) held at 45°C, mixed by gentle vortexing and poured on an Oxoid plate. The plate was rotated and tilted to achieve a uniform distribution on the base agar. These plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 h and streptomycin-independent revertants were counted. In the case of the assay without the S-9 mix, 300 μL PBS instead of 300 μL of the S-9 mix was used.

Positive and negative controls, and sterility testing were assayed throughout the study. For the mutagenicity test, the positive control for standard mutagen contained tester culture and Trp-P-1 in distilled water, and the negative control consisted of tester culture and ethanol. In the antimutagenicity test, the positive control contained tester culture and ethanolic extract of tauco and the negative control consisted of tester culture, Maillard reaction products and only ethanol instead of mutagen. The counts were tabulated after subtracting the spontaneous revertants obtained from the negative controls. Results are expressed as number of revertants per plate. The antimutagenic activity was estimated by measuring the decrease in mutation induced by the mutagen and expressed as inhibition percentages. Antimutagenicity was quantified in terms of inhibition percentage of mutagenicity (PI) and calculated by the formula:

$$\text{PI} = 100 - (\text{number of revertants of test plate}) / (\text{number of revertants of positive control plates}) \times 100;$$

Experiments were repeated twice with duplicates each time.

RESULTS

In the first series of the experiments, the mutagenicity of ethanolic extracts

of sweet and salty tauco were examined. Since sweet and salty tauco extracts did not exhibit significant mutagenicity against *Salmonella typhimurium* TA 98 (data not shown), the streptomycin-dependent (SD) 510 strain was used to assay their mutagenicity.

Ethanolic extracts of the sweet and salty tauco samples heated at 120°C for 45 min and 100°C for 60 min, respec-

Fig. 1 - Dose response of mutagenicity of heated sweet tauco extracts with and without S-9 mix against *Salmonella typhimurium* SD 510 $\square$ 120°C, 45 min with S-9 mix; $\bullet$ 120°C, 45 min without S-9 mix.

Fig. 2 - Dose response of mutagenicity of heated salty tauco extracts with and without S-9 mix against *Salmonella typhimurium* SD 510 $\square$ 100°C, 60 min with S-9 mix; $\bullet$ 100°C, 60 min without S-9 mix.

tively, exhibited a dose-related mutagenicity effect against the SD 510 strain in the range of 5 to 60 μL (mg/mL) tauco extract, equal to 5 to 60 mg tauco per plate (Figs. 1 and 2). Addition of metabolic activation significantly decreased ($P < 0.01$) the mutagenic activity with heated sweet tauco at the concentration of 30 mg per plate (Fig. 1), and heated salty tauco ($P < 0.05$) in the range of 5 to 30 mg per plate (Fig. 2).

Sweet tauco as well as salty tauco samples were heated under the given conditions to examine the formation of heat-induced mutagenicity. The results shown in Fig. 3, indicate that mutagenicity of sweet tauco exhibited higher values with increase in heating temperature from 80 to 120°C; heating time from 15 to 45 min had little effect on the formation of mutagenic compounds, but above 45 min heating did not increase the mutagenicity. The highest mutagenic activities of sweet tauco were observed when heated at 120°C for 45 min. Fig. 4 shows that fairly high induction of mutagenicity was found in the salty tauco heated at a temperature from 100 to 120°C. It was also observed that the heating time ranging from 15 to 60 min increased the mutagenic activities of salty tauco, but no further mutagen formation was observed above 60 min of heating time. The highest mutagenicity was obtained in the case of salty tauco heated at 100°C for 60 min.

The mutagenic activity of sweet and salty tauco was inhibited by the reaction products prepared from lysine-glucose or glycine-glucose and the inhibition was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in the absence of the S-9 mix than in its presence (Table 1). It was also found that the antimutagenic activity of lysine-glucose or glycine-glucose varied between sweet tauco and salty tauco. The lysine-glucose and glycine-glucose products inhibited the mutagenicity of salty tauco on SD 510 by 56.1-96.3%, while the antimutagenic effect on sweet tauco dif-

Fig. 3 - Mutagenicity of the extracts of sweet tauco heated at different times and temperatures against *Salmonella typhimurium* SD 510.

Fig. 4 - Mutagenicity of the extracts of salty tauco heated at different times and temperatures against *Salmonella typhimurium* SD 510.

Table 1 - Inhibitory effect of Maillard Reaction Products^a against tauco induced mutagenicity to *Salmonella typhimurium* SD 510 in the presence or absence of S-9 mix.

Sample	Inhibition (%)			
	Lys-Glc		Gly-Glc	
	with S-9 mix	without S-9 mix	with S-9 mix	without S-9 mix
salty tauco ^b	79.0	96.3	56.1	95.4
sweet tauco ^c	38.4	98.3	27.0	65.1

^a aqueous solution of 1 M lysine (Lys) or glycine (Gly), and equimolar of glucose (Glc) adjusted to pH 7.0 and then heated at 120°C for 30 min.
^b heated at 100°C for 60 min.
^c heated at 120°C for 45 min.

ferred depending on the reaction products, ranging from 27.0-98.3%. Antimutagenicity of Maillard reaction products increased with increased heating temperature, and reached a maximum at 120°C with inhibitory percentages higher than 97.0%, except for the reaction products prepared from glycine-glucose against sweet tauco, where only 67.2% inhibition was observed (Fig. 5). Antimutagenicity of the reaction products prepared under various pHs against the mutagenicity of tauco are shown in Fig. 6. Both the reaction products of lysine-glucose and glycine-glucose prepared above pH 7.0 were found to have fairly high antimutagenic effect on the mutagenicity of sweet and salty tauco toward the SD 510 strain in the absence of the S-9 mix.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The SD 510 strain was used in the mutagenicity assay, due to its advantages over the TA 98 strain, i.e., it gives a sharp response with fewer background colonies, needs only a simple medium, a shorter period of incubation and no requirement for S-9 metabolic activa-

tion in the assay (SHASHIKANT and HOSONO, 1987; HOSONO et al., 1997).

The optimum concentration to obtain the highest number of revertants was found to be 30 mg per plate of heated tauco (Figs. 1 and 2). The higher concentrations of mutagens sometimes led to toxicity and thus reduced the number of revertants.

The addition of metabolic activation had little effect on the mutagenic activities with heated sweet tauco assayed by the SD 510 strain (Fig. 1). One of the advantages of the SD 510 strain is that this strain can be applied to assay the mutagenicity of various mutagens in the presence or absence of the S-9 mix. SHASHIKANT and HOSONO, (1987), working on the SD strains of *Salmonella typhimurium* TA 98 and TA 100, reported that 13 out of 14 spices tested exhibited strong mutagenicity on SD 510 and SD 4 strains even without S-9 activation. They have also studied the mutagenicity of some spices assayed in the presence and absence of metabolic activation and found that the addition of the S-9 mix had no or little effect on the formation of mutagenic compounds in spices such as mace, ginger, cinnamon and white pepper (HOSONO et al., 1987b). The num-

ber of revertants in the heated salty tauco decreased with the addition of S-9 mix (Fig. 2). This is in agreement with the findings by HOSONO et al. (1987b) who found that metabolic activation with S-9 considerably decreased the number of revertants induced by nutmeg in the SD 510 strain, and they suggested that a detoxification mechanism might exist in *in vivo* liver detoxification processes.

The effect of heating temperature on the mutagenicity of sweet and salty tauco shows that mutagenicity increased with increase in heating temperature while a heating time of 15 to 45 min generally increased the mutagen formation (Figs. 3 and 4). These findings indicated that heat treatment strongly enhanced the formation of mutagens in both taucos. In our previous study, we found that glu-

Fig. 5 - Inhibitory effect of the Maillard reaction products prepared under various temperatures against mutagenic heated tauco. Aqueous solution of 1 M lysine (a) or glycine (b), and equimolar of glucose was adjusted to pH 7.0. The reaction mixture was heated at 60, 80, 100 or 120°C for 30 min. Antimutagenic activity of the Maillard reaction products against mutagenic heated tauco (■ salty tauco; □ sweet tauco) was assayed in the absence of the S-9 mix using *Salmonella typhimurium* SD 510.

Fig. 6 - Inhibitory effect of the Maillard reaction products prepared under various pHs against mutagenic heated tauco. Aqueous solution of 1 M lysine (a) or glycine (b), and equimolar of glucose was adjusted pH to 3.0, 5.0, 7.0, 9.0, or 11.0. The reaction mixture was heated at 120°C for 30 min. Antimutagenic activity of the Maillard reaction products against mutagenic heated tauco (■ salty tauco; □ sweet tauco) was assayed in the absence of the S-9 mix using *Salmonella typhimurium* SD 510.

tamic acid was the major amino acid in sweet and salty tauco, and that it may contribute to the increase in the mutagenicity of tauco after heat treatment (USMAN and HOSONO, 1996). This presumption is based on the findings by SUGIMURA et al. (1983) who reported that some mutagenic substances such as heterocyclic amines were formed in products containing glutamic acid during heat treatment, but this presumption needs further study.

The highest mutagenic activities were found for sweet tauco and salty tauco at a dose level of 30 mg/plate after heat treatment at 120°C for 45 min and 100°C for 60 min, respectively (Figs. 3 and 4). Hence, the dose with 30 mg/plate and these heating conditions were selected for the antimutagenicity assay.

Some researchers have reported that Maillard reaction products from different sugars and amino acids prepared under various conditions exhibited antimutagenic activities against mutagens (KATO et al., 1985; LEE et al., 1994; YEN et al., 1992). It has also been reported that these reaction products have antimicrobial activity against some species of selected food-poisoning microorganisms (STECCHINI et al., 1991; 1993) and antioxidant properties (ELIZALDE et al., 1992; ANESE et al., 1993; 1994; PITOTTI et al., 1995; YEN and HSIEH, 1995); substances exhibiting antioxidant activities sometimes show antimutagenic and/or anticarcinogenic properties (AMES, 1983). Antimutagenicity of Maillard reaction products toward the mutagenic tauco assayed by using the SD 510 strain in the absence of the S-9 mix was higher than in the presence of the S-9 mix (see Table 1). These findings are in concordance with our previous results that higher inhibition percentage against Trp-P-1 was observed in both lysine-glucose and glycine-glucose when they were assayed without the S-9 mix than with it (HOSONO et al., 1997). Also the inhibitory effect of the reaction prod-

ucts prepared from lysine-glucose was higher than that prepared from glycine-glucose against the mutagenicity of sweet and salty tauco. This may be due to the fact that lysine generally browns faster than glycine which results in different colour intensity. KATO et al. (1985) reported that antimutagenicity of reduced nondialyzable melanoidin decreased with decrease in colour intensity.

The properties of the products of the Maillard reaction are strongly dependent on the nature of the reactants and reaction conditions, especially pH and temperature (Figs. 5 and 6). It was found that antimutagenic activity of reaction products prepared from lysine-glucose and glycine-glucose increased with increase in heating temperature, and also a higher inhibition was observed when reaction products were prepared under alkaline than acidic pH. Presumably, alkaline catalysts at high pH led to the formation of more colored products and this may have contributed to the higher antimutagenic activity.

In conclusion, data from the present study clearly show that tauco becomes mutagenic after heat treatment, especially at temperatures above 100°C for more than 15 min. Since tauco is a cheap and good source of protein, especially consumed by the people living in West Java, Indonesia, it is suggested that dishes containing tauco be prepared in a short time (less than 15 min) and below 100°C to minimize mutagen formation during cooking. On the other hand, the reaction products of lysine-glucose and glycine-glucose had a strong antimutagenic property against the mutagenicity of heated tauco assayed by the SD 510 strain. In this regard, it is of great concern to isolate and identify the active antimutagenic compounds of the Maillard reaction prepared from lysine or glycine with glucose under a moderate heating temperature of 100°C for 30 min.

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